

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 5.4: DEVELOPMENT PLAN FOR CO-EXTRACTION

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Public summary of
confidential report

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Due Date: 30.06.2024

Submission Date: 18.07.2024

Accepted Date: 18.07.2024

Deliverable Reference: D5.4

Work Package / Task:

WP5 / T5.3 Co-extraction of ulvans,
proteins and minerals for *Ulva* sp.

Keywords:

algae, circular economy, ecosystem
services, *Ulva* sp., green macroalgae

Summary:

A pilot scale extraction was carried out on 60 kilograms of fresh *Ulva* sp. received from the Portuguese partner ALGAplus. After aqueous extraction, screening by ultrafiltration membrane was done to separate the compounds within the liquid extract according to their molecular sizes. All fractions were finally analysed to determine the composition. Two ulvans rich fractions were obtained (Purity > 50% DM), one with high molecular weight (> 150 kDa) and another one with low molecular weight (150 > X > 15 kDa). The 1 kDa filtrate yielded a mineral-rich fraction whose elementary composition has been partially characterized. The residual biomass from the process proved to be the protein rich but insoluble fraction. This first pilot trial produced interesting results and needs now to be optimised.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060379. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor REA can be held responsible for them.